

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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1 Executive summary

This report provides an overview of NextGEMS model performance in simulating tropical air-sea interaction systems. Our analysis encompasses an examination of the general circulation patterns in both the ocean and the atmosphere at large scales. Furthermore, we assess the models' capabilities in replicating smaller-scale, short-term phenomena, including the Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO), tropical cyclones, boundary layer profiles on selected grid points, and the interaction between latent heat flux and surface winds. Finally, we evaluate air-sea feedback mechanisms, focusing on how the small-scale extreme precipitation events influence the ocean's mixed layer.

2 Conclusion & Results

We compared SR-ESMs, focusing on model development cycles 1-3 with data summarised in Table 3. Our assessment covered large-scale ocean and atmosphere circulation, the atmospheric boundary layer profiles on selected grid points, latent heat flux sensitivity to surface wind, intra-seasonal variability, tropical cyclones, and ocean mixed layer feedback. The main results are listed as follows:

1. The SR-ESMs reproduce general features of the ocean circulation, the sea surface temperature distribution and the sea-ice cover reasonably well, but with biases that are often similar to coarse resolution GCMs. During the development cycles, we diagnosed improvement in ICON's SST distribution and the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation and in the seasonal cycle of Southern Hemisphere sea-ice concentration in IFS-FESOM. The evaluation of mixed layer depth (MLD) shows that in Cycle 3 of ICON, MLD biases decrease near the equator but increase in the northern tropical Atlantic compared to Cycle 2. In high-resolution Cycle 3 of FESOM, MLD biases decrease near the equator but increase in the North Brazil Current region.
2. We find that tropical precipitation biases persist in SRGCMs. First, tropical precipitation amounts are systematically overestimated in tropical rainbands, which appears closely related to biases in surface enthalpy fluxes. Second, the zonally averaged distribution is shifted southward, which is in line with biases found in the cross-equatorial atmospheric energy flux. Finally, the double-ITCZ bias is identified as unimproved w.r.t. standard GCMs, which we find reflected in an anomalous Hadley circulation.
3. The MJO is better simulated in cycle 3 of IFS model, especially the version run at higher resolution, in simulating MJO, and equatorial Kelvin and Rossby waves, which are too weak in the ICON model. The 30-year length of some simulations in cycle 2 allows a better estimation of the spectral content than the 5-year length of cycle 3 simulations.
4. Higher-resolution simulations in cycles 2 and 3 better match observed tropical cyclone frequency, with ICON showing less sensitivity to resolution. IFS outperforms ICON in representing central pressure and wind speed relationships. Both IFS (2.5 km and 4.4 km) and ICON (5 km) simulate 24-hour intensification rates effectively.

5. Both ICON and IFS models represent the main characteristics of the vertical structure of the atmospheric boundary layer under trade-cumulus conditions in the region east of Barbados. This comprises a variety of grid resolutions and physical parameterizations considered in the simulations. Both models show greater sensitivity to parameterization than for grid resolution changes, which is promising for certain grid independence in SRMs. In the ICON model, the Smagorinsky turbulence model led to a better representation of the winds compared to using the total turbulence energy scheme, which was designed for coarser-resolution applications and overestimated the wind speed.

6. Latent heat flux is overestimated in both IFS and ICON models. The overestimation can be attributed to the absence of weak surface latent heat flux during calm conditions. It is also influenced by the significant sensitivity of surface latent heat flux to changes in surface wind speed, especially during strong wind conditions.

7. In the tropical Atlantic, sea surface salinity (SSS) distributions from cycle 2 and cycle 3 runs show good agreement with the satellite-derived distributions. However, particularly during the boreal summer period, zonal bands of low SSS consistently appear in the tropical Atlantic ITCZ indicating too localized precipitation patterns.

8. Precipitation events exceeding 20 mm d⁻¹ can shallow the mixed layer depth, leading to accelerated ocean currents. This phenomenon results from the production of lower-salinity water during precipitation, which reduces density and sharpens density gradients, impeding vertical mixing and allowing momentum to be trapped in a shallow layer.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	yes

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	no

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP6	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify and evaluate key ocean and marine atmosphere features in the SR-ESM simulations of all three development cycles. (O1)	yes
To validate the marine planetary boundary layer representation of the SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	yes
To provide ocean initial conditions for the coupled SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	no
To provide developments towards an ocean mixed layer scheme adequate for SR-ESMs. (O1)	yes
To create numerical tools that generate output streams useful to the planetary boundary layer, ocean mixed-layer and fisheries communities. (O1,O3)	yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Model	Configuration	Horizontal Resolution	Simulated Period from 20.01.2020
Cycle 1			
ICON	dpp0066	5 km	13 months
IFS-FESOM2		4 km	
IFS-NEMO		4 km	
IFS-NEMO		9 km	
IFS-NEMO-DEEPon		4 km	
Cycle 2			
ICON	ngc2009	5 km	2 years
ICON	ngc2012	10 km	10 years
IFS-FESOM	tco3999-ng5	Atm: 2.5 km/ Oce: 5 km	8 months
IFS-FESOM	tco2559-ng5	Atm: 4 km/ Oce: 5 km	1 year
IFS-NEMO	tco1279-orca025	Atm: 9 km/ Oce: 25 km	1 year
Cycle 3			
ICON	ngc3028	5 km	5 years
IFS-FESOM	IFS_4.4-FESOM_5	Atm: 4 km/ Oce: 5 km	5 years
IFS-FESOM	IFS_9-FESOM_5	Atm: 9 km/ Oce: 5 km	1 year
IFS-NEMO	IFS_9-NEMO_25	Atm: 9 km/ Oce: 25 km	5 years
IFS-NEMO	IFS_28-NEMO_25	Atm: 28 km/ Oce: 25 km	5 years

Table 3: models and experiments

4.1 Ocean mean state, sea-ice cover, and the large-scale ocean circulation across the three development cycles

This section compiles a selection of general features evaluating the ocean's mean state in three NextGEMS development cycles. The purpose is not to demonstrate the capabilities of the high-resolution models to simulate (sub)mesoscale features, but to describe the background state under which more process-oriented analyses are performed. Results of the latter will be provided in separate deliverables. We note that the relatively short duration of the simulations (one to five years, table 3) limits the information value. The mean state of large-scale ocean features may reflect largely the quality of the spin-up procedure and the model drift may still be large at a short time after the coupling.

Here we mainly evaluated the model performance in simulating the mean state of Sea Surface Temperature (SST), Mixed Layer Depth (MLD), Sea ice and the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). Sea surface temperature, mixed layer depth and sea-ice properties are the most important ocean-related quantities in a coupled simulation since they determine the atmosphere-ocean fluxes and their variability. The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation is an important carrier of heat and fresh water in the Atlantic.

4.1.1 SST

The annual mean SST fields for the three cycles of the ICON experiments and for cycles 2 and 3 from the IFS-FESOM (4km/5km) are shown in Fig. 1 in comparison with the HadISST observational data set. While the models reproduce the specific features of the ocean circulation, for example, the northward tilted isotherms in the subpolar North Atlantic reflecting the Gulf Stream system (not shown), the SSTs are generally too cold over most of the globe. In particular, in ICON cycle 1, we diagnose severe biases in the sub-polar North Atlantic and in the tropical oceans. Throughout the development cycles, the ICON solutions improved substantially. The bias in the sub-polar North Atlantic is much reduced reflecting not only a better general tuning of the atmosphere but also a better representation of the Gulf Stream circulation. However, a cold bias at low latitudes remains, exceeding -2°C in the cold tongue of the equatorial Pacific and the western Atlantic. These biases will have an impact on the representation of the ITCZ and the development of Tropical Instability Waves. In contrast, IFS-FESOM shows a warm bias over the lower latitudes with SSTs exceeding 30°C in the western tropical Pacific and the Indian Ocean, but biases rarely exceed -2°C . There is no pronounced difference between the last two development cycles in IFS-FESOM. A more thorough evaluation of stand-alone ocean simulations with respect to the tropical oceans and the sensitivity to ocean mixing parameters have been provided in Deliverable 6.5.

4.1.2 Mixed layer depth distributions

The ocean mixed layer is in direct contact with the atmosphere, and it modulates the propagation of heat and mechanical energy into the deep ocean. The depth of the mixed layer (MLD) influences the sea surface temperature and salinity, which means that the coupling of the atmo-

Figure 1: Annual mean SST from HadISST (upper left) and differences between the NextGEMS simulations and HadISST from the coupled 5km ICON runs (three nextGEMS development cycles), and cycle 2 and 3 from IFS-FESOM.

sphere and the ocean is sensitive to MLD biases. In General Circulation Models (GCMs) and coupled climate models, tropical MLD is simulated too shallow (Huang et al., 2014). This persistent bias is one of the unsolved issues in climate modelling. One of the potential sources of bias is vertical mixing parameterisations. The mixing scheme implemented in all ocean components across all cycles is the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE, Gaspar et al., 1990) vertical mixing parameterisation. Between cycles 2 and 3, the value of TKE parameter c_k is altered from 0.2 to 0.1. This parameter determines what fraction of turbulent kinetic energy is used for vertical diffusion of momentum and tracer. It is therefore of interest to investigate how this change influences the simulated depth of the mixed layer.

The annual mean mixed layer depth (MLD) distributions in the tropical Atlantic Ocean are shown in Figures 2 (Cycle 2) and 3 (Cycle 3). The observed distributions are computed based on Argo vertical temperature and salinity profiles (Wong et al., 2020). ICON MLD is defined as the depth where the sea water is 0.03 kg m^{-3} denser than the surface. FESOM MLD is defined according to Levitus: the depth where the sea water is 0.125 kg m^{-3} denser than the surface. In ICON, MLD biases in cycle 3 are reduced around the equator but amplified in the northern tropical Atlantic compared to cycle 2. Similarly, high-resolution cycle 3 FESOM MLD biases are reduced around the equator, but the deep bias in the region of the North Brazil Current is amplified. The magnitude of the biases is not significantly dependent on the model.

Figure 2: Annual mean distributions of the mixed layer depth in the tropical Atlantic based on Argo observations and Cycle 2 simulations.

Figure 3: Annual mean distributions of the mixed layer depth in the tropical Atlantic based on Argo observations and Cycle 3 simulations.

In Deliverable 6.5, the stand-alone tropical ocean simulations are analysed in detail. No significant dependence of the MLD on the tested TKE parameters was found in these forced simulations. Consistent with this analysis, the MLD distributions in the tropical Atlantic do not show a systematic improvement between cycle 2 and 3 simulations.

4.1.3 Sea ice

Figure 4: Northern Hemisphere sea-ice concentrations for March and September from the OSI-SAF satellite product (upper left), three development cycles of ICON (upper right, middle row) and the latest two development cycles of IFS-FESOM (lower row).

The Nordic Seas and the Arctic Ocean are characterized by the inflow of warm and saline waters of Atlantic origin along the coasts of western Europe and Norway and the outflow of cold and fresh surface waters along Greenland and through the Canadian Archipelago. This asymmetry in ocean circulation is reflected in the Northern Hemisphere sea-ice cover (Fig. 4) ice-free conditions as far north as Svalbard and the White Sea as can be seen in sea-ice observations, e.g., from the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT, EUMETSAT, 2015) Satellite Application Facilities on Ocean and Sea Ice (OSI SAF) data set (Fig. 4, upper left). The OSI SAF data also indicate ice-free conditions over the central Labrador Sea throughout the year. The seasonal cycle in the Northern Hemisphere is such that most of the Arctic Ocean remains ice-covered throughout the year with reduced coverage along

Figure 5: Southern Hemisphere sea-ice concentrations for March and September from the OSI-SAF satellite product (upper left), three development cycles of ICON (upper right, middle row) and the latest two development cycles of IFS-FESOM (lower row).

the rim. These general features are well captured in all ICON simulations. The representation of the seasonal cycle is considerably better than in the coarse resolution ICON-ESM (Jungclaus et al., 2022). Despite a generally warmer mean state in cycle 3, the sea-ice cover is slightly overestimated as can be seen by the boreal winter ice concentration in the Greenland and Iceland Seas and around Svalbard. Owing to the short duration of the simulation it is, however, difficult to determine if these changes are due to different model tuning or just expression of year-to-year variations in the coupled climate system. IFS-FESOM shows a more compact sea-ice distribution and overestimates the extent in a similar way as ICON, i.e., too much sea-ice in the Greenland Sea and around Svalbard. The latest IFS-FESOM cycle reproduces a reduced sea-ice extent in summer, which aligns more closely with the observations. The sea-ice cover in the Southern Hemisphere (Fig. 5) is characterized by a pronounced seasonal cycle, where the sea-ice extent retreats almost to the Antarctic coast in the Australian Basin in austral summer, whereas summer sea ice prevails in the Wedell Sea basin and the Bellinghousen basin. All ICON simulations reproduce the summer and winter distribution well with little distinction between the three cycles. In the cycle 3 simulation from IFS-FESOM, the seasonal cycle and the sea-ice distribution are reproduced very similarly to ICON and we diagnose an improvement with respect to cycle 2.

4.1.4 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation

Figure 6: Annual mean Atlantic Meridional Overturning streamfunction from three development cycles of ICON (left) and the latest development cycle of IFS-FESOM.

The AMOC streamfunction (Figure 6) represents the zonally integrated view. The North Atlantic Deep-Water (NADW) cell is oriented clockwise and includes the downward motion associated with deep water formation in the Labrador Sea and Nordic Seas, as well as the overflows across the Greenland-Scotland Ridge at 60°N . The maximum strength of the AMOC exceeds 16 to 20 Sv at approximately 40°N and we diagnose an export of about 14 to 16 Sv at 30°S . The lower, counter-clockwise oriented cell is associated with Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) entering the Atlantic and upwelling in the basin. Although the overturning stream function cannot be compared directly with observation, the RAPID project has provided measurements of the respective flow components at 26.5°N (Smeed et al., 2018). At 26.5°N , the observations suggest a maximum strength of 16 ± 4 Sv, roughly at 1000 m depth and a zero-crossing of the profile at 4500 m. The ICON simulations reproduce the strength of the NADW cell well, where the cycle 3 run shows the highest values and the deepest (more realistic) zero-crossing. The Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) cell is weaker in the experiments with the stronger NADW circulation. In cycle 3, the simulated AABW maximum is slightly above 2 Sv, while observation-based estimates point to values of 6 Sv (Ganachaud and Wunsch, 2003) or 8 Sv (Talley et al., 2003). For IFS-FESOM, data for the calculation of AMOC were only stored for cycle 3. Generally, the model produces a stronger AABW and a weaker NADW cell compared to all ICON realizations. In comparison to the RAPID estimates, the strength of the NADW cell is underestimated with a maximum overturning of less than 12 Sv at 26.5°N .

4.2 Tropical Precipitation and Circulation

We report on the representation of tropical precipitation and its biases as well as on the governing large-scale zonally averaged meridional circulation, namely the Hadley cell, in the nextGEMS storm-resolving global climate models (SRGCMs). Both phenomena are closely related: at least in the zonal mean, there is a clear association between precipitation and rising motion in the ascending branch of the Hadley cell. The most prominent and long-standing among tropical precipitation biases is the double-ITCZ bias, which is characterized by excessive precipitation in the Southern Hemisphere, especially over the southeastern Pacific and South Atlantic, and too little precipitation close to the equator (Zhang et al., 2019; Tian and Dong, 2020). SRGCMs came along with expectations of improved tropical precipitation biases (Stevens et al., 2019; Hohenegger et al., 2020), as parameterizations of convection in coarse resolution GCMs were viewed as flawed and unable to drive mesoscale tropical circulations. We will here use specific precipitation indices to objectively estimate precipitation biases and then relate those to metrics derived from the atmospheric energy balance framework (e.g., Schneider et al., 2014).

4.2.1 Models and Data

In the present analysis, we investigate nextGEMS simulations of the project's modelling cycles 2 and 3 (see Table 3). Four simulations are using the ICON model and five simulations are using the IFS model. Three of them operate on grids with resolutions smaller than 5km compromising on the simulation period (2-5 years). The other simulations are integrated for up to 30 years with resolutions of about 9km. In the following, each simulation will be identified with the following naming convention: modelling cycle (C2 or C3), model name (ICON, NIFS or FIFS) and horizontal resolution.

We use as observational references ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) for the 1979-2014 period for top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiative and surface radiative and turbulent enthalpy fluxes, and meridional moist static energy transport, and GPCP (Adler et al., 2018) for the same period for precipitation. We also include AMIP6 and CMIP6 ensembles (Eyring et al., 2016) for the same historical period. Biases in TOA radiative fluxes are used in reference to *Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System* (CERES, see Loeb et al., 2018) and biases in surface enthalpy fluxes over the sea are assessed in reference to the SEAFUX observational dataset (Robertson et al., 2020).

4.2.2 Tropical Precipitation and its Biases

Figure 7a) shows the temporal and zonal mean precipitation for all nextGEMS simulations individually and in panel b) for ensemble averages over ICON and IFS simulations, together with results from AMIP6, CMIP6, ERA5 and GPCP. All nextGEMS models simulate excessive precipitation in the tropics. Additionally, they feature a clear double-ITCZ bias, with excessive precipitation in the SH relative to the NH and too little precipitation close to the equator. Notice how both SH and NH precipitation peaks (around 8°S and 8°N, respectively) appear to be slightly displaced poleward relative to observations. Relative to GPCP, ERA5 tends to overestimate

tropical precipitation, interestingly more so in the NH than in the SH peak. NextGEMS biases are similar to those found in CMIP6. Not surprisingly, AMIP6 simulations, where SSTs are prescribed, perform better in terms of the double-ITCZ bias. In the following, we explore possible sources of tropical precipitation biases by using the energetic framework, which ties the position and shifts of the ITCZ, embedded in the ascending branch of the Hadley cell, to the meridional energy fluxes needed to achieve or restore energy balance (e.g., Kang et al., 2008; Frierson and W.-T. Hwang, 2014; Schneider et al., 2014; Adam et al., 2016; Adam et al., 2018).

Figure 7: Zonally and temporally averaged precipitation [mm day⁻¹] for a) the individual nextGEMS models and b) for nextGEMS, AMIP6 and CMIP6 ensemble averages, along with ERA5 and GPCP.

In Figures 8 and 9 we show the annually averaged precipitation over all simulated years for the individual models as well as for the ensembles along with biases against GPCP for the entire tropics. In the spatial pattern, we find that the double-ITCZ bias originates primarily from biases in the western Pacific, with excessive precipitation south of the Equator and too little precipitation close to the Equator.

In Figure 9 we show the nextGEMS ensemble average (ICONs+IFSSs) and we note that tropical precipitation is systematically overestimated: mean tropical precipitation flux P is 4.9 mm day⁻¹ for the nextGEMS ensemble (ICONs+IFSSs), with respect to 3.6 mm day⁻¹ for GPCP (see Figure 8 bottom right panel).

While several metrics have been introduced in the literature to quantify biases in the tropical precipitation distribution, here we use two metrics that have been used specifically for the double-ITCZ problem. The first one is the precipitation asymmetry index A_P (Y.-T. Hwang and Frierson, 2013), which measures the hemispheric asymmetry of the tropical precipitation distribution, defined as:

$$A_P = \frac{[P]_{0^\circ-20^\circ N} - [P]_{20^\circ S-0^\circ}}{[P]_{20^\circ S-20^\circ N}}, \quad (1)$$

with $[P]_{\phi_1-\phi_2}$ being the zonal and area-weighted mean precipitation P within latitudes ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 . For a single precipitation peak in the NH (SH), $A_P = 1(-1)$.

Further, we use the equatorial precipitation index E_P (Adam et al., 2016) in order to estimate the hemispherically symmetric component of the tropical precipitation distribution, defined as:

$$E_P = \frac{[P]_{2^\circ S-2^\circ N}}{[P]_{20^\circ S-20^\circ N}} - 1. \quad (2)$$

The equatorial precipitation index relates near-equatorial [2°S;2°N] rainfall to the overall tropical

Figure 8: (Left) Temporally averaged precipitation [mm day⁻¹] in the tropics (30°S-30°N) for all nextGEMS simulations. (Right) Bias w.r.t. GPCP. Bottom row: ERA5 and GPCP. Golden lines indicate the ITCZ position north and south of the equator, identified as the latitude of local precipitation maxima, and the magenta line indicates the center of mass of the tropical precipitation distribution (precipitation centroid).

precipitation [20°S;20°N]. For a double ITCZ with no precipitation at the equator $E_P = -1$. For uniform tropical precipitation $E_P = 0$. As precipitation becomes more equatorially peaked, E_P becomes positive. Note how both indices, being normalized, remove the effect of overall excessive tropical precipitation, and only measure possible biases in its distribution.

In Figures 8 and 9, values of A_P and E_P are noted on top of the corresponding panels. For

Figure 9: nextGEMS ensemble mean of temporally averaged precipitation [mm day^{-1}] in the tropics (30°S - 30°N), and CMIP6 and AMIP6 ensemble means, along with their biases w.r.t. GPCP.

nextGEMS simulations A_P is generally smaller (0.11) w.r.t. to both ERA5 (0.19) and GPCP (0.19), objectively quantifying the tendency for these models to produce too much precipitation south of the Equator relative to the northern hemisphere. Overall, the nextGEMS ensemble mean ($A_P = 0.11$) performs better than CMIP6 (0.05), but worse than AMIP6 ($A_P = 0.2$). Still, we note that for AMIP6 the patterns of precipitation biases are both substantial and very similar to those seen in the other modelling systems.

In GPCP observations E_P is 0.14, while the nextGEMS ensemble mean features a value of -0.10 , again reflective of excessive precipitation in the SH and suppressed precipitation at the equator. In this regard, both CMIP6 ($E_P=0.05$) and AMIP6 ($E_P=0.07$) perform notably better than the nextGEMS SRGCM ensemble.

4.2.3 The Atmospheric Energy Balance

The vertically integrated atmospheric energy balance is a statement that, over a long temporal mean, any net energy input (or loss) in an atmospheric column through its top and bottom needs to be balanced by divergence (convergence) of energy flux by atmospheric motions:

$$\nabla \cdot \langle \vec{u}h \rangle = NEI \quad (3)$$

where \vec{u} is the horizontal velocity vector, with zonal and meridional components u and v , respectively, $h = c_p T + L_v q + gz$ is the moist static energy and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ represents a mass-weighted vertical integral. On the right-hand side, the net energy input NEI to the column is given by:

$$NEI = R_{TOA} - F_{SFC} - R_{SFC}, \quad (4)$$

where R_{TOA} is the net top-of-atmosphere radiative flux, F_{SFC} is the surface turbulent enthalpy flux (latent plus sensible heat fluxes) and R_{SFC} is the surface net radiative flux.

We assume that the atmospheric energy budget is closed and we compute the meridional component of the divergent energy flux $[vh]^\dagger$ implied by the net energy input as

$$[vh]^\dagger = \delta_y \nabla^{-2} [NEI]. \quad (5)$$

with $[\cdot]$ denoting a zonal average. One fundamental assumption in the energetic framework is that the ascending branch of the Hadley cell is approximately co-located with the latitude where the column-integrated atmospheric energy transport (AET) vanishes, also known as the energy flux equator (EFE), and where the meridional divergence of AET maximizes (e.g., Kang et al., 2008; Schneider et al., 2014). Given that the Hadley cell's ascending branch also coincides with the region of maximal precipitation or the ITCZ, these arguments provide a powerful connection between the energetics, the atmospheric circulation, and the ITCZ position and associated biases in climate models (e.g., Adam et al., 2016; Adam et al., 2018). In particular, the ITCZ position has been argued to be anti-correlated with the cross-equatorial atmospheric energy transport, given that in the tropics energy and moisture transports are primarily accomplished by the Hadley circulation and energy is transported in the direction of the Hadley cell's upper branch. Hence, a northward (southward) shift of the ITCZ is associated with anomalous southward (northward) energy transport across the equator.

Figure 10 shows the temporal and zonal means of NEI and its components. The shape of NEI in the tropics is characterized by peaks south and north of the equator, and a minimum right on the equator. NextGEMS models reproduce these double-peak patterns fairly well. However, they tend to overestimate the NEI magnitude across the tropics. The decomposition into contributions from TOA radiative and surface fluxes shows how these biases primarily arise from biases in surface enthalpy fluxes.

Figure 11 shows the annually averaged NEI and its components for the entire globe along with their biases w.r.t. ERA5, for the NextGEMS ensembles. All over the tropics and subtropics, biases in NEI are mostly positive. Reflective of the Pacific cold tongue bias, biases over the equatorial Pacific are negative (See Section 4.1). Biases in surface fluxes, particularly in the

Figure 10: Panels a-d): Zonally and temporally averaged net energy input (NEI) [$W m^{-2}$] and its components, the net radiative flux at top of atmosphere, $RTOA$ [$W m^{-2}$] and at the surface, $RSFC$ [$W m^{-2}$] and the net surface turbulent enthalpy fluxes, $FSFC$ [$W m^{-2}$]. The dashed black curve represents CERES observations in panel b) and SEAFUX observations over the ocean in panel d).

surface enthalpy fluxes ($FSFC$) control the overall bias in NEI . TOA radiative fluxes ($RTOA$) are well simulated. We find $FSFC$ being overestimated in the northern Atlantic and Pacific, over the maritime continent and on the west coast of Africa, which must be seen as part of the reason for the systematic overestimation of tropical precipitation. In the bottom panel of Figure 11 we show $FSFC$ biases w.r.t. the observational dataset $SEAFUX$ and find that the overestimation is even greater, although the Pacific cold tongue bias remains. The biases identified in surface enthalpy fluxes are largely in line with the SST biases presented in Section 4.1.

Figure 12 shows the zonally and annually averaged "implied" meridional energy transport, computed from Eq. 5 for the nextGEMS ensemble average. In addition to the meridional energy flux implied by NEI , we also show separately the transport implied by the TOA and surface fluxes, and the associated EFE (ϕ_{EFE}), for both the nextGEMS ensembles and ERA5. We also show mean precipitation and its centroid, ϕ_{cent} , defined as the centre of mass of the precipitation distribution (e.g., Frierson and W.-T. Hwang, 2014) for the nextGEMS ensemble. Consistent with energetic arguments, the double-ITCZ bias manifests itself with a smaller southward cross-equatorial energy transport and a southward displacement of the EFE (by 2 degrees latitude), respectively. These findings are also consistent with biases in the precipitation asymmetry index A_P (see Section 4.2.2).

Figure 11: Net energy input (NEI) [$W m^{-2}$] and its components, the net radiative flux at top of atmosphere, RTOA, and at the surface, RSFC, and the net surface enthalpy fluxes, FSFC, and its biases w.r.t. ERA5. The bottom panels show the nextGEMS ensemble's bias in FSFC w.r.t. the observational dataset SEAFUX, and the bias in RTOA w.r.t. CERES.

In Figure 13 we show how tropical precipitation metrics (A_P and E_P) correlate with energy-based metrics (AET_0 and NEI_0 , respectively). Adam et al., 2016 have shown that in CMIP5 models and observations A_P is negatively correlated with the cross-equatorial atmospheric energy transport AET_0 and E_P is positively correlated with the equatorial net energy input NEI_0 , in agreement with theoretical expectations (Bischoff and Schneider, 2014). In the nextGEMS simulations, the relationship between A_P and AET_0 appears to be weaker than in the CMIP5 ensemble (with correlation coefficient $R \approx -0.6$ vs $R = -0.85$ in CMIP5), and no significant correlation is found between E_P and NEI_0 across the entire simulation suite. However, as ev-

Figure 12: The implied meridional energy transport derived from the meridional gradient of the Inverted Laplacian of NEI and its components $RTOA$, $RSFC$ and $FSFC$. Vertical lines indicate the latitude of the energy flux equators, ϕ_{EFE} , of NEI and its components, for both the nextGEMS ensemble and ERA5. The green line represents the zonal average of precipitation flux for the nextGEMS ensemble, and the vertical line indicates the latitude of the precipitation centroid, ϕ_{cent} .

ident in Figure 13 (right), a tighter relationship emerges if individual models and/or individual simulation cycles are considered. This is an intriguing result, which we will explore further in future work.

Figure 13: Relation between the annual mean tropical precipitation asymmetry index A_P and cross-equatorial atmospheric energy transport AET_0 (left) and between the annual mean equatorial precipitation index E_P and the equatorial atmospheric net energy input NEI_0 (right) in the nextGEMS simulations. Ensemble means are shown in open black circles, and values from CMIP5 and ERA5 are also shown for reference.

4.2.4 The Hadley Circulation

The meridional mass stream function and the associated energy transport for the ICON simulation ngc2009, characterized by a grid spacing of 2.5 km in the atmosphere and a 2-year simulation period, is shown in Figure 14. We chose this specific simulation as one with the strongest double-ITZC bias ($A_P = 0.1$ and $E_P = -0.28$). Consistent with the existence of two precipitation maxima on either side of the equator, the Hadley cell features a two-cell structure, with two ascending branches at about 8°S and 8°N , respectively. Such structure is not seen in observations (e.g., Dima and Wallace, 2003).

Figure 14: (Top) Zonally averaged meridional moist static energy transport (shading) and streamfunction of the mean meridional circulation (line contours, kg s^{-1}). (Bottom) Zonally averaged precipitation, meridional moist static transport explicitly computed from the simulation, and implied meridional moist static energy transport. Vertical lines represent latitudes of the precipitation centroid (green), of the precipitation maximum (blue), and of the EFE of the explicit (red) and implied (yellow) meridional moist static energy transport.

4.2.5 Summary

We summarize the relationship between tropical precipitation and energy-based metrics, together with their normalized relative biases in Figure 15.

Firstly, the double-ITCZ bias, a stubborn bias that has persisted across generations of climate models, does not show evidence of improvement in the nextGEMS SRGCMs. The energetic framework allows to link this bias to biases in the distribution and hemispheric asymmetry in the

net energy input. Interestingly, we find that biases primarily arise from biases in surface enthalpy fluxes rather than from biases in TOA radiative fluxes. Resolving processes in the uppermost ocean layers (mixing processes) and the air-sea interaction (wind stress, radiation, ...), from which enthalpy fluxes result, appear to remain a major challenge at storm-resolving numerical resolution.

Secondly, we tried to objectively quantify biases in the tropical precipitation distribution in terms of antisymmetric, A_P , and symmetric components, E_P , which have been argued to be constrained by near-equatorial energetic metrics (namely, the cross-equatorial energy transport and the equatorial net energy input). The negative biases of ϕ_{cent} and A_P are both indicative of excessive precipitation in the SH w.r.t. GPCP. The negative (southward) bias in the ICTZ position is accompanied by a same-signed bias in ϕ_{EFE} , confirming covariations between the two metrics arising from energetic constraints. Additionally, we find A_P to be anti-correlated with the cross-equatorial energy transport. Negative biases in E_P are indicative of suppressed equatorial precipitation. Against theoretical expectations, these biases do not appear to be correlated with the equatorial net energy input for the ensemble as a whole. We do however find evidence of stronger correlations across individual model runs and simulation cycles. This is a point we will keep addressing in future work.

Figure 15: Summary of precipitation and energy balance metrics ϕ_{cent} [°], ϕ_{EFE} [°], E_P [-], A_P [-], NEI_0 [Wm^{-2}], AET_0 [PW] for all nextGEMS models, CMIP6, AMIP6, ERA5 and GPCP. Color shading indicates relative biases w.r.t. either ERA5 for energetic properties or GPCP for precipitation properties, normalized by their respective maximum value.

4.3 Madden-Julian Oscillation

The Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO) is the main mode of tropical climate variability in the atmosphere at intra-seasonal timescales. However, its simulation in climate models remains a challenge (Jiang et al., 2020). We analyse the representation of MJO in NextGEMS simulation by calculating the frequency-wavenumber spectra of the symmetric component of the outgoing longwave radiation for summer and winter months in observations and in cycle 2 and cycle 3 model simulations (Figs. 16 and 17), following the methodology detailed in Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999. As with previous works (e.g. Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999), the observations show strong spectral content in the sector corresponding to the MJO (frequencies smaller than 0.05 cycles per day and westward wavenumbers smaller than 5 cycles per complete circle). The spectral content also shows maxima related to other convectively coupled waves, such as the equatorial Rossby waves (eastward propagating signals with a maximum spectral content of around 4 cycles per complete circumference and the same MJO frequency band), and equatorial Kelvin waves (which align with the westward dispersion curves with frequencies between 0.1 and 0.3 cycles per day) (Fig. 16ab). A footprint of tropical disturbances can also be seen in observations for boreal summer (frequencies of 0.3 cycles per day and westward propagations of around 10 to 15 cycles per complete circumference).

Consistently with observations, the two long runs of the ICON model in cycle 2 show spectral content above the background in the MJO and equatorial Kelvin and Rossby spectral sectors, with stronger MJO content for boreal winter (Fig. 16c-f). The spectral content is, nevertheless, strongly underestimated in the simulations, suggesting the models struggle to simulate intra-seasonal variability. Winter MJO is stronger in rthk001 with respect to ngc2013 simulation, which could be due to changes in the atmosphere-ocean coupling and/or climatology in these two twin experiments. The spectral content above the background for summer tropical disturbances is more consistent with observations, though with too high wavenumbers.

The simulation of MJO and equatorial Kelvin and Rossby waves is not improved in the cycle 3 ICON run (Fig. 17ab). The spectral peaks are still strongly underestimated, with a boreal summer MJO even weaker than the equatorial Rossby waves. Results are more noisy than for cycle 2, due to the smaller number of years in the simulations (30 years in cycle 2 and only 5 in cycle 3).

Though also noisy due to the short length of the simulations, the estimated strength of the spectral content of the main symmetric intra-seasonal variability waves in cycle 3 IFS simulations is closer to observations (Fig. 17c-f). Kelvin waves are underrepresented in the coarser configuration (IFS_28-FESOM_25) but greatly improved in the higher resolution run (IFS_4.4-FESOM_25). For both runs, the MJO shows strong spectral content for wavenumbers higher than 5 cycles per circumference, suggesting less coherence in the spatial structure of the MJO with respect to observations. The runs show an unrealistic stronger MJO spectral content for boreal summer than for boreal winter.

All in all, the analysis suggests a better performance of IFS model, especially the version run at higher resolution, in simulating MJO, and equatorial Kelvin and Rossby waves, which are too weak in the ICON model. In addition, runs longer than 5 years would improve the estimation of the spectral content.

Figure 16: Zonal wavenumber-frequency spectrum for the outgoing longwave radiation symmetric about the equator (between 15°S and 15°N) in observations (NOAA OLR Liebmann and Smith, 1996, period used 1994-2021, a and b) and cycle 2 ICON simulations ngc2013 (c and d) and rthk001 (e and f) for boreal summer (May to October, first column) and winter (November to April, second column). Frequency in the Y axis is in units of cycles per day and zonal wavenumber in X axis is in units of cycles per complete circle, with positive (negative) values meaning eastward (westward) propagating waves. Shown in shaded is the ratio of the actual spectrum to the background one. The black box shows the spectral region corresponding to the MJO

Figure 17: Zonal wavenumber-frequency spectrum for the outgoing longwave radiation symmetric about the equator (between 15°S and 15°N) in cycle 3 simulations for ICON ngc3028 (a and b) and IFS_28-FESOM_25 (c and d) and IFS_4.4-FESOM_5 (e and f) for boreal summer (May to October, first column) and winter (November to April, second column). Note the limited number of seasons (5) used in the calculations wrt Fig. 16. Frequency in the Y axis is in units of cycles per day and zonal wavenumber in X axis is in units of cycles per complete circle, with positive (negative) values meaning eastward (westward) propagating waves. Shown in shaded is the ratio of the actual spectrum to the background one. The black box shows the spectral region corresponding to the MJO

Figure 18: Annual-mean TC statistics in IBTrACS observations over the period 1980–2020 (black) and nextGEMS simulations: (a) TC frequency, n_{TC} , (b) TC days, d_{TC} , and (c) ACE, Σu_{10}^2 , scaled by 10^{-4} . Bars represent global statistics; the hatched areas represent the Northern Hemisphere. Tropical depressions were excluded (i.e., statistics were computed for all systems with a lifetime-maximum intensity exceeding 17 ms^{-1}).

4.4 Tropical cyclone: frequency, intensity, and tracks

Tropical cyclones were tracked in cycle 2 and 3 simulations using the objective feature-tracking algorithm TempestExtremes (Ullrich et al., 2017; 2021), as follows. Candidate points were identified by an increase in sea-level pressure of $\geq 20 \text{ hPa}$ over 5.5° (great-circle distance) from the given pressure minimum (i.e., a closed-contour criterion). The presence of an upper-level warm core is identified by Z_{250hPa} and $Z_{500hPa} \leq 6 \text{ m}$ over 6.5° from pressure a minimum point to distinguish tropical from extratropical low-pressure systems. Additional criteria were employed to merge candidate points, where necessary, and stitch candidates into tracks: minimum tropical cyclone duration, the maximum allowed gap in a given track (e.g., to allow for cyclone weakening when a system moves over land), and maximum displacement allowed between candidate points. nextGEMS simulations were evaluated against IBTrACS (best-track) data (Knapp et al., 2010), and the evaluation was performed only for tropical cyclones whose lifetime-maximum intensity exceeds 17 ms^{-1} .

Annual-mean tropical cyclone frequency, n_{TC} , and tropical cyclone days, d_{TC} show sensitivity to resolution and also differ between IFS and ICON across cycles 2 and 3 (Fig. 18). Resolution sensitivity is clear in IFS: simulated n_{TC} in both cycle 2 and 3 simulations is closer to observations at higher resolutions, although the 4.4 and 2.5 km cycle 2 simulations are short. IFS simulations in cycle 3 at 9 km also reveal an increase in n_{TC} with FESOM at 5 km (compared with NEMO at 25°). ICON simulates n_{TC} and d_{TC} values that exceed observations in cycle 2, but this improves in cycle 3. ICON shows less sensitivity to atmospheric resolution. ACE, a cumulative measure of tropical cyclone intensity and activity, is well simulated by IFS at 4.4 km and by ICON at zoom 10 (6 km) in cycle 3, although the performance is better globally than for

Figure 19: Relationship between per-TC v_{max} and p_{min} for IBTrACS observations over the period 1980–2020 (black) and nextGEMS simulations, with marginal distributions shown in the top (v_{max}) and right-hand (p_{min}) panels (note the log scales). TC categories, defined by p_{min} according to Klotzbach et al. (2020) and Bourdin et al. (2022), and according to the National Hurricane Center’s operational definitions for v_{max} , are delineated by grey, dashed lines. The legend gives the atmospheric horizontal resolution of each simulation in parentheses.

Figure 20: Distribution of 24-hour v_{max} changes (positive = intensification; negative = weakening) in IBTrACS observations (black) and nextGEMS simulations, with (inset) a detailed picture of intensification rates defined as RI (i.e., $\geq 15.4 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, a threshold indicated by the grey, dashed line). (b) Mean RI ratio, a measure of RI occurrence defined as the ratio of 24-hour v_{max} changes above the RI threshold to total v_{max} changes. Bar labels and legend give the atmospheric horizontal resolution of each simulation in parentheses.

the Northern Hemisphere.

The relationship between tropical cyclone central pressure and near-surface wind speed is better represented by IFS than by ICON (Fig. 19). At 4.4 km, IFS captures the observed relationship, albeit the sample size of the most intense storms is insufficient to assess significance. ICON simulates deep tropical cyclones, but their wind speeds are too weak for a given central pressure, and this model error deteriorates from cycle 2 to cycle 3.

Rapid intensification (RI) is a rare but high-impact phenomenon. IFS at 2.5 km (cycle 2) and 4.4 km (cycle 3) simulates near-observed distributions of 24-hour intensification rates (Fig. 20a). ICON at 5 km (cycle 2) also simulates RI. The RI ratio, a measure of the frequency of RI, simulated by IFS at 4.4 km in cycle 3 is close to the observed ratio (Fig. 20b). In cycle 2, ICON approached the observed value at 5 km, but this metric also deteriorates in cycle 3. Owing to the rarity of RI events, longer simulations will help establish confidence in these preliminary findings.

4.5 The atmospheric boundary layer during the EUREC⁴A field campaign

One advantage of storm-resolving models is that they facilitate comparison with observations, which can help to understand better the realism of these simulations and the standing challenges. In this project, we compare simulation results with measurements from the EUREC⁴A field campaign (Stevens et al., 2021). This campaign provides detailed information about the marine boundary layer, which is key for the air-sea interaction. It also focuses on the tropical region, which is an important element of the climate system because of its relevance in cloud radiative feedback.

The EUREC⁴A field campaign took place during January and February 2020 in the region east of Barbados, which is representative of the Atlantic trade winds. This campaign includes island-based measurements at the Barbados Cloud Observatory (BCO), which hosts several common meteorological and remote sensing instruments (Stevens et al., 2016). The BCO is located on the island's upwind (eastern) shore at Deebles Point (13.16°N, 59.43°W). It samples nearly undisturbed trade-wind conditions from the "Tradewind Alley" (Stevens et al., 2021). In this report, for conciseness, we present a summary of the evaluation of the vertical profiles based on radiosondes launched at the BCO (Stephan et al., 2021). Further discussion is presented in deliverable 6.2.

The model results come from the nextGEMS simulations using the ICON and IFS models under the three development cycles (table 3). The results were composed considering the period in which there were simultaneous simulation results and observational data, which was from 21 January to 17 February 2020.

4.5.1 Results

The analysis starts with the results for the IFS and ICON simulations with around 5 km horizontal resolution from cycle 2. Specifically, the tco2559-ng5 experiment in IFS with 4-km horizontal

Figure 21: Vertical profiles of (left to right) specific humidity, relative humidity, virtual potential temperature, and wind speed at the Barbados Cloud Observatory site from January 21st to February 17th, 2020. Observations are shown in gray, and simulation results are shown in red. The solid lines show the average, and the shadings show the standard deviation. The profiles are for tco2559 and ngc2009 simulations from the nextGEMS cycle 2 (Table 3).

resolution in the atmosphere and the ngc2009 experiment in ICON with 5-km horizontal resolution (Fig. 21). The simulated profiles at the BCO represent the main characteristics measured by the radiosondes. It is particularly impressive that ICON can produce such an adequate estimate using the Smagorinsky model without tuning. A common deviation for both models is the representation of a colder (around 1 K) vertical profile compared to the observations, and it is consistent with global values reported in other projects. The ICON simulation represented a drier cloud layer between 1-2 km height, and a moister layer above it, related to stronger turbulent vertical mixing in the simulations. The IFS simulations did not show this deviation, which might be related to the use of convective parameterizations. However, the ICON model in its storm-resolving “Sapphire” configuration (Hohenegger et al., 2023) did not use convective parameterizations in their physics. On the other hand, IFS represented the first kilometer drier than the measurements, and it might be connected to the weaker winds, which produce a weaker surface latent heat flux.

The sensitivity of the simulation results to using distinct horizontal resolutions and parameterization schemes is shown for ICON in the three development cycles (Fig. 22). The comparison among ICON cycle 2 simulations is particularly interesting since it is possible to determine the impact on the results with the change in horizontal resolution (cycle 2-ICON-10km-ngc2012-Smagorinsky vs. cycle 2-ICON-5km-ngc2009-Smagorinsky) and model physics (cycle 2-ICON-10km-ngc2012-Smagorinsky vs. cycle 2-ICON-10km-ngc2013-TTE). In this way, the impact of the increase in horizontal resolution from 10 km in ngc2012 to 5 km in ngc2009 and the change in the turbulence models from Smagorinsky in ngc2012 to Total Turbulent Energy (TTE) in ngc2013 is investigated.

The change in the turbulence scheme from Smagorinsky to TTE led to an average increase of 26% for the wind speed, which is associated with turbulent vertical mixing. In the ngc2013 simulation, stronger turbulent vertical mixing transports momentum from the free troposphere downward and enhances the winds in the boundary layer, overestimating the measured wind speeds. This turbulent vertical mixing is also responsible for warming up the boundary layer, as seen in the ngc2013 vertical profile. Although ngc2013 represented a warmer vertical profile in better agreement with measurements, it could result from a discrepancy in the representation of some processes. Such processes could be a stronger vertical mixing and the representation of fewer clouds, which would permit more short-wave radiation from the sun to reach the surface and heat it.

The ICON model showed less sensitivity to changes in the storm resolving range's grid spacing than model physics. This suggests some degree of grid convergence with certain properties. This conclusion can also be applied to the IFS model results, although the results are not shown here for conciseness.

The vertical structure for the ICON simulations in the three cycles (Fig. 22) is generally similarly represented in all the cycles. It means the results were not too sensitive to the model configuration changes among the cycles. An improvement in the third development cycle was the representation of a drier-free troposphere compared to the previous cycles, which is in better agreement with the measurements.

Comparing the IFS results across the simulation cycles allowed us to verify that the IFS_4.4-FESOM_5-cycle3 profiles are colder and moister above 1.5 km, and the wind speed is weaker than in the cycle 2 simulation with the same resolution (tco2559-ng5), deviating more from the measurements. The source of the differences in temperature and humidity between these simulations mostly comes from using the deep convection scheme in cycle 3. These results are not shown here for conciseness; see deliverable 6.2 for more details.

4.6 Wind, evaporation feedback in experiments with different resolutions

As shown in Fig. 23a, in observations, the average 10m wind speed at the grid point 0°N 160°E registers at 4.7 m/s. This value is properly represented in the model simulations. The simulated wind speeds fall within a range of 4.26 m/s to 4.97 m/s, with the most precise simulation achieved in IFS_9-FESOM_5 at 4.82 m/s (Fig. 23e). In terms of observational data, the mean Surface Latent Heat Flux (SLHF) at the same grid point is measured at 109.3 W/m². However, in all simulation runs, this value is consistently overestimated, ranging from 119.9 W/m² to 133.6 W/m², with the best simulation achieved in IFS_9-NEMO_25 at 119.8 W/m² (Fig. 23d). During calm conditions, when the 10-meter wind speed approaches zero, the surface latent heat flux still maintains a relatively elevated value, typically exceeding 40 W/m². In contrast, observational data shows this value to be below 20 W/m².

In high wind speed conditions, the latent heat flux continues to exhibit a linear increase with wind speed. In the ICON model (Fig. 23b), the latent heat flux ranges between 120-300 W/m² when the surface wind speed reaches approximately 10 m/s. Similarly, the IFS model, specifically IFS_9-FESOM_5 (Fig. 23e) and IFS_4.4-FESOM_5 (Fig. 23f), demonstrates comparable

Figure 22: Vertical profiles of (top to bottom) relative humidity, virtual potential temperature, and horizontal wind speed for the ICON simulations at the Barbados Cloud Observatory site from January 21st to February 17th, 2020. The solid line shows the average, and the shading shows the standard deviation. Observations are shown in gray, and simulation results are shown in red. The profiles are from the three nextGEMS cycles (Table 3).

Figure 23: Two-dimensional Histogram of sensible heat flux (SLHF in W/m^2) and 10m wind speed (WS10 in m/s) on grid point $0^\circ N$ $165^\circ E$. a) TAO, b) ICON ngc3028, c) IFS_28-NEMO_25, d) IFS_9-NEMO_25, e) IFS_9-FESOM_5, f) IFS_4.4-FESOM_5

performance, with latent heat flux ranging from 100-300 W/m^2 at wind speeds up to 10 m/s . In the case of IFS_4.4-FESOM_5 (Fig. 23f), the latent heat flux extends from 100-340 W/m^2 at 10 m/s wind speed. However, in models like IFS_28-NEMO_25 (Fig. 23c) and IFS_9-NEMO_25 (Fig. 23d), the distribution of surface latent heat flux aligns more closely with observational data. In IFS_28-NEMO_25 (Fig. 23c), SLHF exhibits a linear increase with wind speed and reaches 340 W/m^2 when the wind speed reaches 12 m/s . In IFS_9-NEMO_25 (Fig. 23d), a similar behaviour is observed, with SLHF reaching 340 W/m^2 when the wind speed reaches 15 m/s . As a conclusion, the overestimation of surface latent heat flux can be attributed to two primary factors. Firstly, it is caused by the absence of weak surface latent heat flux during calm conditions. Additionally, it is influenced by the significant sensitivity of surface latent heat flux to changes in surface wind speed, especially during strong wind conditions. These findings are consistent not only at grid point $0^\circ N$ $160^\circ E$ but also extend to other locations, including grid point $0^\circ N$ $220^\circ E$ (Fig. 24), and are observable throughout the entire tropical region (Figures not shown).

Figure 24: Two-dimensional Histogram of sensible heat flux (SLHF in W/m^2) and 10m wind speed (WS10 in m/s) on grid point $0^\circ N$ $220^\circ E$. a) TAO, b) ICON ngc3028, c) IFS_28-NEMO_25, d) IFS_9-NEMO_25, e) IFS_9-FESOM_5, f) IFS_4.4-FESOM_5

4.7 Sea surface salinity

Throughout the different stages of SR-ESM development, the sea surface salinity (SSS) from the simulations was compared to SSS data from satellite retrievals to investigate the representation of precipitation and of advection of low saline waters from riverine inputs in the surface layer. The sea surface salinity (SSS) plays a fundamental role in the Earth's water cycle, the density-driven global ocean circulation and climate. Several physical processes such as evaporation and precipitation, ocean salt transport by the large-scale, mesoscale and submesoscale circulation, near-surface turbulent mixing and river discharge contribute to the determination of SSS.

Here, the SSS distribution of the NextGEMS simulations is evaluated against observations in the tropical Atlantic. In this region, SSS has a very contrasting distribution with low SSS between the equator and $10^\circ N$ due to heavy precipitation under the ITCZ and high SSS near the centre of the large-scale subtropical gyres where evaporation exceeds precipitation. In addition, freshwater runoff from the Amazon, Congo and Niger create plumes with low SSS. The Amazon River

accounts for more than one-third of the total river discharge in the Atlantic Ocean and exhibits strong seasonal variability reaching its maximum in May-June (Dai and Trenberth, 2002). During late boreal summer and fall, the North Equatorial Countercurrent sets eastwards between 4°N to 9°N (Stramma et al., 2005). It carries parts of the Amazon River plume water towards northwest Africa (Coles et al., 2013) and thus reinforces low SSS due to precipitation within the ITCZ situated between 4°N and 10°N during this season.

Figure 25: Comparison of daily averaged sea surface salinity distributions (in psu) of three SR-ESM runs during July 1st, about 5 months after spin-up (ICON ngc2009 in upper left, ICON ngc3028 in upper right, and IFS_4.4-FESOM_5 run in lower right panel), and sea surface salinity from satellite retrievals during the July 1st, 2020 (lower right panel).

An optimum interpolated product that combines observations from NASA's Aquarius SAC-D and Soil Moisture Active-Passive (SMAP) satellite missions (Melnichenko et al., 2016) provided by the Asia-Pacific Data-Research Center (IPRC Technical Note No. 7) was compared to the simulations. These data are available as global distributions of SSS on a 0.25-degree spatial and 4-day temporal grid. Satellite retrievals were bias-corrected against Argo floats and salinity records from moored buoys prior to merging. The uncertainty of the merged product globally is about 0.19 psu (root-mean-square).

Initial analyses of ICON cycle 1 run revealed anomalous freshwater advection from the mouth of the Amazon and other rivers, which led to an unrealistic representation of the freshwater budget in the tropical Atlantic (not shown). The problem was fixed in the ICON cycle 2 and cycle 3 runs by spreading the river discharge over several grid points in the estuary.

Overall, SSS distributions from cycle 2 and cycle 3 runs showed good agreement with the satellite-derived SSS. However, particularly during the boreal summer period, zonal bands of low SSS w.r.t the satellite observations consistently appeared in the region of the ITCZ (cf.

Fig. 25). These differences were more pronounced in the ICON runs (ngc2009 and ngc3028) compared to the cycle 3 IFS_4.4-FESOM_5 run. As shown in section 4.2.2 the ICON and IFS-FESOM simulations exhibit a small positive bias of the average precipitation flux in the tropical North Atlantic only (Fig. 9). This suggests that during boreal summer zonal cloud patterns within the ITCZ may be too organized in the simulations. Although similar differences in SSS patterns are also seen during the other seasons, they are less pronounced.

The spreading of the Amazon, Congo and Niger river plumes were generally well represented in the cycle 3 simulations. Anomalous low SSS distributions in the eastern equatorial Atlantic present in the ICON cycle 2 simulation that may have originated from anomalous precipitation or Congo River plume advection were not present in the later runs. Also, low SSS at the western boundary south of the equator in the ICON runs (Fig. 25) vanishes in subsequent years and thus may only reflect an initialization effect.

4.8 Effect of extreme precipitation on surface ocean freshwater budgets

4.8.1 Setting the problem

Stratification of the ocean plays a role in the transfer of momentum from the air to the upper ocean. A stratified ocean could dampen the deepening of the mixed layer depth if the forcing is not enough to break the ocean stratification. In an atmospheric convective environment, short-wave radiation absorption is reduced, meaning that stratification due to warming layers is also reduced, leaving changes in salinity as the main contributor to the stratification. Then, is this mechanism simulated in an Earth System model at km-scale? If this is the case, how much should it precipitate to see an effect on the stratification?

4.8.2 Method

We use the following method to understand the impact of precipitation on the stratification of the upper ocean and the impact on current acceleration in simulation ngc3028 (ICON).

For every grid point, we use a threshold of 5 mm d^{-1} to categorize days as dry ($< 5 \text{ mm d}^{-1}$) and wet ($> 5 \text{ mm d}^{-1}$) days. We identify the first day surpassing the threshold. If there are no days precipitating greater than 5 mm d^{-1} in the following five days, this event is considered a precipitation event with a duration of one day.

If there are days precipitating more than 5 mm d^{-1} in the five following days, the last day surpassing the threshold is considered the end of the precipitation event. Then, the evaluation is repeated until finding that the event's last day precedes five days with precipitation less than 5 mm d^{-1} . The duration of this type of event is the difference of days between the last and the first days, precipitating more than 5 days.

To compare the effect of precipitation in stratifying the upper ocean, we compute the mean of the thickness of the mixed layer depth (MLD), salinity, and surface ocean currents vertically integrated from the surface to the base of the MLD during the precipitation event. For each

Figure 26: Heat map of a) Number of precipitation events with precipitation more than 5 mm d^{-1} . Precipitation events are grouped in ranges of mean intensity (y-axis, logarithmic scale) and duration of the event (x-axis). b) Difference in the vertically integrated salinity in the mixed layer depth between during and five days before the precipitation event. c) Difference in the thickness of the mixed layer depth between during and five days before the precipitation event. The gray lines in a-b) indicate isolines of the total amount of water produced by precipitation events.

precipitation event, the time average is computed. This procedure is also applied for the five days before the precipitation event.

4.8.3 Results

In the tropical Atlantic (60°W - 20°E , 20°N - 20°S) 521159 precipitation events fulfill the conditions described in section 4.7.2. These events are grouped according to their mean intensity and the duration of the event (Figure 26a). The mean intensity is calculated by dividing the total amount of precipitation of the event by the duration of the event. The color shading in Figure 26a indicates the number of events in a certain range of mean intensity (y-axis) and range of duration (x-axis).

Figure 26b shows a decrease in salinity in the MLD during the precipitation event. The signal is strong ($dS < -0.4 \text{ psu}$) for precipitation intensities greater than 20 mm d^{-1} . The drop in salinity is related to a shallowing of the MLD, strongly observed with precipitation events with intensities greater than 20 mm d^{-1} (Figure 26c).

The ocean currents also accelerate in the MLD during a precipitation event (Figure 27a). The signal is strong for precipitation events with a mean intensity greater than 20 mm d^{-1} . In that region of the diagram (Intensity $> 20 \text{ mm d}^{-1}$), events lasting one day present a decrease in the wind forcing (Figure 27b). For events lasting more than one day, an increase in the wind forcing accompanies current acceleration in MLD (Figure 27b).

Those types of events could be explained by momentum being trapped in a shallow layer. An intensification of the wind-forcing in a well-stratified ocean does not deepen the MLD but accelerates the currents (Intensity $> 20 \text{ mm d}^{-1}$ and duration > 1 day). Even if the wind-forcing

Figure 27: Heat map of a) difference in the vertically integrated ocean current in the mixed layer depth between during and five days before the precipitation event. b) Difference in wind velocity above the ocean surface between during and five days before the precipitation event. The gray lines in a-b) indicate isolines of the total amount of water produced by precipitation events.

decreases, shallowing the MLD allows for the acceleration of the current.

4.8.4 Conclusion

Our analysis shows that precipitation events with mean intensities greater than 20 mm d^{-1} can shallow the mixed layer depth. In those events, ocean currents present an acceleration while the MLD shallows even with an increase in the wind forcing. This could be explained by the stratification. The low-salty water injected by precipitation into the upper ocean decreases the salinity, and simultaneously, the density. This affects the profile of density, sharpening the gradient and preventing the mixing between the upper and deeper ocean. Thus, momentum is trapped in a shallow layer, allowing the acceleration of currents.

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)

This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)
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6.2 Ensuring the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

Each subsection will be published as a paper individually. We will also reorganise the deliverable as a model introduction paper to describe the Tropical airsea interactions in the kmScale Resolution Earth System Models.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

We're facing data storage issues, particularly with high-frequency (6-hourly or daily) output in cycles 1 and 2. These problems hinder our ability to compare model performance across all three development cycles.

Most of our runs are shorter than 5 years, which poses challenges in evaluating the climate state and interannual variability. The mean state of of large-scale ocean features may reflect the quality of the spin-up procedure and model drift may still be large for a short time after the coupling. Additionally, the performance assessment of intraseasonal variability is also constrained by the short run lengths.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable (D6.1) evaluated the NextGEMs models from cycles 1 to 3. A more detailed evaluation of ocean simulation, focusing on tropical ocean mixing parameters are provided in the report of D6.5. The model evaluation paves the way for further work which will apply the model output for further analysis in WP7. The work of model evaluation can also provide valuable suggestions for further model development.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19 – 22 October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- WWRP/SERA "Weather and Society" Conference 28 February – 11 March, 2022, online
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01 – 03 April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26 June – 02 July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31 June – 06 July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04 – 06 April 2023
- Storylines presentation, EGU, 23 – 28 April, Vienna, Austria
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29 May – 02 June 2023 in Madrid, Spain

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>